

Do Adverse Events Influence Time Preferences? Evidence from Smallholder African Farmers

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Abstract

Time preferences play a critical role in the agri-food value chains of low-income countries, impacting the choices of local operators, including innovation uptake. This paper estimates the association between smallholder farmers' individual characteristics their exposure to diverse adverse events, and their intertemporal choices, using lab-in-the-field experiments conducted across five African countries. We find that farmers who have experienced social setbacks during the previous year are more likely to be patient. This suggests that time preferences may vary over time, particularly when farmers are exposed to social distress (e.g., food shortage, health issues, violence, or crime). Moreover, we find gender to be a prominent factor associated with farmers' time preferences. These findings hold direct implications for both research and public policy initiatives aimed at influencing agricultural choices in the aftermath of social distress. By understanding the factors influencing time preferences, more targeted and effective strategies can be developed to support smallholder farmers, thereby enhancing the resilience of agri-food value chains in low-income countries.

Highlights

- Time preferences are key drivers of farmers' behaviour.
- Linking farmers' adverse events to patience levels is underexplored.
- We conducted incentivised field experiments in five African settings to elicit time preferences.
- Farmers who faced social setbacks in the past year are more likely to be patient.

JEL Classification: D90, C93, O55, Q12

Keywords

Africa, Economic experiment, Time preferences, Patience, Risk preferences, Social setback.

1. Introduction

Farmers' livelihood and farming activities are highly vulnerable to socio-economic challenges and climate change-related events. Factors such as rainfall variability and vulnerable health conditions lead to uncertainty and frequently to poor yields, which in turn cause a decline in farmers' revenues (Crawford et al., 2003). African smallholder farmers are particularly exposed to these adverse conditions (Naazie et al., 2023), with and potentially economic consequences. Indeed, Africa heavily depends on its approximately 33 million smallholder farmers, who produce 75–90% of major food commodities in sub-Saharan Africa (Demmler, 2020). Beyond food production, smallholder farms are vital for providing employment and sustaining livelihoods, especially for vulnerable groups such as rural women (Gollin, 2014). For instance, in African low-income countries, smallholder farmers account for roughly 60% of the national workforce, underscoring their central role in economic and social stability (African Development Bank Group, 2023).

Intergovernmental actions and frameworks such as the 2023 Comprehensive African Agriculture Development Program, the Alliance for a Green Revolution in Africa and, from a broader perspective, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), have been deployed to mitigate the effects of climate change on farmers and improve rural livelihoods (Mohammed et al., 2023; Mapfumo et al., 2013). While these initiatives have the potential to enhance farmers' livelihoods in the long-term (Antwi-Agyei & Nyantakyi-Frimpong, 2021; McKenzie, 2013; Padel, 2001), they often entail complex decision-making processes by smallholder farmers, whose outcomes are affected by the individual farmer's attitude towards change (Ayisi et al., 2022; Rogers, 2010). Given the contribution of smallholder farmers to the African food system and their exposure to stressors, it becomes thus crucial to understand farmers' behaviours in times of distress. This paper takes a step in that direction.

Farmers' behaviour depends on a wide range of factors. First, demographic characteristics and farm-specific features are widely recognised as key determinants. Second, a growing body of research has investigated the role of risk propensity, beliefs, trust, and attitudes as additional elements impacting farmers' decisions (de Oca Munguia & Llewellyn, 2020; Iyer et al., 2020;

Rippo & Cerroni, 2023). Finally, time preferences have been identified as a significant factor, and an increasing number of studies have explored their role in shaping farmers' behaviours, questioning their consistency over time especially during periods of crisis and uncertainty (e.g., Cassar et al., 2017; Di Falco & Vieider, 2022; Kirby, 2009; Kirby et al., 2002; Krupka & Stephens, 2013). Conversely, other scholars argue that time preferences remain stable over time, even in the face of socio-economic change (Drichoutis & Vassilopoulos, 2021; Hardardottir, 2017). Given these contrasting perspectives, providing additional cross-country evidence on the matter becomes highly relevant.

In our work, we aim to assess whether time preferences remain stable among a large cross-country sample of African farmers who may have experienced various (perceived) adverse events. In so doing, we build on Cassar et al. (2017) and Di Falco & Vieider (2022) into the impact of shocks and adverse events on time preferences. We focus on the following research questions: (i) what types of adverse events affect smallholder farmers in the studied African contexts? (ii) To what extent these different adverse events, as perceived by the farmers, relate to time preferences? Both questions are particularly relevant for policymakers, agro-service providers, and research organizations working in Africa, which are often tasked with designing organizational and technological innovations to enhance the resilience of local food-farming systems and their ability to adapt to stressors. For these interventions to be effective in the long term, substantial changes in farmers' behaviours and in their responsiveness to critical events is often required (Mapfumo et al., 2013).

Our empirical analysis relies on standardised surveys and in-the-field experiments. Data were collected in 12 rural areas from five African countries (Kenya, Morocco, Tanzania, Tunisia, and Uganda). To study the association between farmers' time preferences and their adverse experiences, we employ both Poisson regressions and joint estimation with risk preferences using maximum likelihood estimators (à la Andersen et al. 2008). Both specifications include environmental, social, and economic setbacks experienced by individual smallholder farmers as the main predictors. Our results point to a significant relationship between farmers' patience and their exposure to setbacks of social nature (e.g., food shortage, health issues, violence or crime). Smallholder

farmers in our sample who have experienced adverse social events are more likely to exhibit higher levels of patience. Additionally, we identify a significant gender effect, with female farmers showing greater patience than their male counterparts.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. An overview of the literature guiding the development of our research, as well as the contributions we make to the literature are presented in Section 2. Section 3 provides an overview of the study areas and describes the methodological procedures employed. In Section 4, we present the data used in the study along with the main descriptive statistics. Section 5 details the empirical strategy and reports the key findings on the associations between farmers' adverse experiences and their time preferences. Section 6 concludes.

2. Literature and contribution

Intertemporal choices are decisions with consequences that materialise over time (Berns et al., 2007). Understanding the motivations behind such choices is crucial in economics so to predict decisions such as spending and investments, purchasing habits, health and education choices, to mention a few. Interpersonal choices play a critical role at many levels of the agri-food value chain. On the supply side, they influence farmers' access to credits and payments (e.g., farmers with limited access to savings may prefer delayed payments when they are given in regular instalments; Casaburi & Macchiavello, 2019; Kramer & Kunst, 2020); farmers' willingness to adopt innovations, e.g., new crops (farmers with liquidity constraints might be reluctant to adopt innovations that generate a return only in the medium-long term; Bocquého & Jacquet, 2010); or farmers' choices regarding the marketing channels for agricultural outputs (e.g., less risky private output markets offering immediate payments can be more attractive for poorer farmers with impatient behaviours; Kamoyo & Makochekanwa, 2018). On the demand side, time preferences can influence consumers' propensity to purchase food with varying taste and nutritional profiles (impulsivity vs. self-control over long-term health benefit; Barlow et al., 2016; Muñoz Torrecillas et al., 2018) as well as consumers' spending habits, which are related to budgetary constraints (Hall et al., 1980).

Literature has shown that individual patience is a key driver – along with risk, temptation, uncertainty, and feelings of anticipation – in shaping time preferences of individuals (Casari & Dragone, 2010). Impatience is the characteristic of individuals tending to forego larger rewards in the future and opt for smaller and sooner rewards. Previous research has documented heterogeneity in the degree of patience when measured across different types of individuals (Frederick et al., 2002). Comparing impatience levels (and related discount rates) can be of interest for market segmentation based on individuals' different geographical, cultural, and demographic characteristics (Rambaud & Torrecillas, 2016). Impatience is also dependent on the context, and on the framing of the investment problem, as shown by experiments using different designs (e.g., small vs. larger payments, short vs. long delays, different resources or items assessed, and framing; Zauberman & Urminsky, 2016).

Impatience is a critical variable in farming activities as it is associated with decisions in terms of innovation uptake, among others. Farmers' patience is influenced by several situational and individual factors ranging from socio-demographic variables to personal experiences, and risk attitudes. Le Cotty et al. (2014) showed that elicited individual time preferences of farmers in Burkina Faso correlate with fertilizer use: more impatient farmers are less likely to modify their agricultural inputs. Teklewold (2012) studied the association between farmers' impatience and their propensity to apply manure, finding significant linkages between time preferences and the use farmers make of manure (selling vs. internal use). In Uganda, Bartos et al. (2018) assessed the relationship between poverty and time preferences in a controlled longitudinal experiment, showing that concerns over poverty-related problems increase farmers' impatience. Di Falco et al. (2019) studied the effect of income on time preferences in an Ethiopian farming system, finding that farmers' income variations increase individual farmers' discount rates, and thus their impatience.

Finally, there have been a series of studies which looked at the relationship between risk attitudes and time preferences (e.g., Clot et al., 2016; Julia Ihli et al., 2022). According to these studies, and consistently with the broader literature on risk aversion, farmers who are more risk-tolerant tend to also be more patient. In particular, the works by Andersen et al. (2008) and Andreoni & Sprenger (2012) provide seminal insights into the relationship between risk and time preferences,

challenging the assumption that time discounting can be straightforwardly interpreted without considering its interplay with risk preferences. The joint elicitation method developed by Andersen et al. (2008) has been widely used in studies examining time and risk preferences in the farming sector, as well as their heterogeneity with respect to socio-demographic characteristics (Fischer & Wollni, 2018; Liebenehm & Waibel, 2014; Sawosri & Mußhoff, 2020) and is also adopted in this study alongside other modelling approaches.

In addition to the abovementioned behavioural traits, shocks and adverse events such as floods, droughts, and pest invasion can modify farmers' time preferences, thus affecting their propensity to invest in farming activities (Cassar et al., 2017). For instance, literature reports an overconfident approach to risk by farmers who have faced adverse events (Barsbai et al., 2022; Finger et al., 2022). Although the literature has studied farmers' risk aversion and its determinants, precise measurements of how farmers' former experiences to distresses affect their patience levels and thus their propensity to innovate is currently understudied. In general, previous studies not specifically focusing on farmers show that impatient behaviour might be the result of past negative experiences and shocks (Cassar et al., 2017). Barnett & Breakwell (2001) found that individuals' negative experiences weaken their propensity to take risks but, on the other hand, individuals experiencing certain setbacks repeated in the long term might become less sensitive to future adverse events and show more patience. Demographic factors combined with occurrence of adverse events influence individuals' patience and time preferences (Coletta et al., 2019). A review of the topic by Chuang and Schechter (2015) revealed that the literature lacks consensus regarding the impact of past economic or climatic shocks on time preferences. In this perspective, we believe that it is valuable to seek reconciliation by presenting additional and cross-country evidence on the association between farmers' individual characteristics and experienced setbacks, and their time preferences, drawing on a large sample of African farmers.

Through this study, we contribute to the experimental literature on agricultural time preferences in three ways. First, we deliver new field evidence on the relationship between farmers' experiences and worries and their time preferences. This evidence is particularly valuable for designing

effective policy interventions. A significant association between negative experiences and patience levels would suggest that time preferences vary over time, particularly when farmers face distress. Varying time preferences in the aftermath of adverse events implies that interventions by researchers and policymakers (e.g., technological or organisational innovations) to respond to farmers' distresses (e.g., famines) might be more or less likely to be accepted by individual farmers depending on their exposure to the distress. This topic has received limited attention in the literature to date.

Second, our study provides evidence of this associations relying on a wide cross-country sample in five rural settings from both northern African (Morocco and Tunisia) and sub-Saharan countries (Kenya, Tunisia, and Uganda), thus allowing comparability. Systematic and coherent protocols for eliciting farmers' time preferences in large cross-country studies have been identified as a promising area for future research in a recent review by Wuepper et al. (2023), which primarily focused on studies involving European and North American farmers. Additionally, our experiment involved in-person samples of smallholder farmers, which are generally excluded from behavioural and experimental economic studies executed in laboratory or online settings (e.g., European Commission, 2021; Tjernström et al., 2021).

Third, our study contributes to the growing strand of literature on incentivised experiments on time preferences. A key question in time preference elicitation studies is whether incentivization can help mitigate the hypothetical bias. The main disadvantage of hypothetical choices, as noted in Frederick et al. (2002), is that they may predict inaccurately what participants would do if outcomes were real. Wuepper et al. (2023) found a limited effect of incentivization on the discount rate, which tends to be higher in unincentivised games. Cardenas and Carpenter (2008) emphasise the importance of real incentives while acknowledging the broader challenges of implementing experiments in developing country contexts, such as situations where trust in the institutions delivering the experiment may be lacking. According to Chuang & Schechter (2015), while risk preference experiments are often difficult for participants to understand, time preference experiments—being simpler—tend to perform better than survey-based measurements. While we do

not claim to make a methodological contribution with this article, we aim to enrich the understanding of time preferences involving monetary rewards by providing additional evidence from a broad cross-country sample of rural areas in Africa.

3. Materials and Methods

In this section, we describe our geographical settings and subject pools (3.1). We then detail the survey and experimental design and related procedures (3.2).

3.1 Study areas and subject pool

The data used in this study were collected in the framework of an international research and innovation project.¹ They were collected in 12 rural areas from five African countries (Kenya, Morocco, Tanzania, Tunisia, and Uganda) from April till December 2021.² The rural areas and their geographical boundaries were purposively selected by project partners based on the local agricultural productions and their suitability for the demonstration of innovations being developed in the project. Within each region, the project established so called “food hubs”, i.e., “communities of local operators making joint research and development decisions and enabling the adoption of innovations” (Carloni et al., 2023). As a preliminary step, and before implementing any other project activities, we collected data on farm conditions and behaviours to establish a baseline for the successful dissemination of various innovations. In this study, we use these data.

In each region, small crop farmers (or fish farmers, depending on the local focus) were recruited through stratified random sampling, with strata based on age, gender, and farm size. When one gender (usually females) represented less than one third of the reference population, the group was oversampled to shed light on dynamics and conditions that would otherwise be overlooked, in line with the requirements of the funder. Survey questionnaires were administered in all regions,

¹ (Omitted for review).

² At the time of the data collection, no COVID-19-related lockdown was in place in the studied countries. The sanitary requirements followed by the experimental teams during the data collection did not impact farmers' responses according to the assessment of these teams.

for a total of 5,456 responses. In one region from each country, behavioural experiments were also implemented, either jointly with the survey (four countries), or separately but in a coordinated manner (Tunisia). Overall, 2,393 of the above farmers took part in the behavioural experimental sessions.

The location of the 12 regions is shown in the map in Figure 1, while Table 1 provides an overview of their geographical, cultural, and socio-economic background characteristics, further detailed in the following of this section. Given the focus of the project, our goal was not to gather a representative sample of each country's farming population but rather of producers in each food hub area. Therefore, our data cannot be used to make inference on the composition or the behavioural characteristics of the national farming population. Equally, the local samples are not fully comparable and for this reason, in our cross-country models we control for country- and session-fixed effects. Nevertheless, the stylised facts detected may extend beyond the borders of the single areas or countries.

Figure 1. Geographical location of the 12 food hubs (names in parenthesis) and their respective macro administrative levels.

1 **Table 1.** Socio-economic descriptors of the 12 food hubs.

Food hub	Country	Macro administrative level	Population (year) ^a	Main agricultural productions	Average farm size (ha)	Farmers' type	Sample size (survey)	Sample size (experiments)
Mukurweini	Kenya	Nyeri County	759,164 (2019)	Cereals, pulses, root crops, arrow roots, industrial crops, horticultural crops.	0.75	Crop	505	505
Kitui	Kenya	Kitui County	759,164 (2019)	Maize, sorghum, and millets, pulses (green grams, cowpeas and pigeon peas), root crops (cassava, sweet potatoes and arrow roots; industrial crops (cotton, sisal).	0.5	Crop	482	-
Kisumu	Kenya	Kisumu County	1,155,574 (2019)	Lake capture fishing, aquaculture farming, maize, sorghum, and millet, industrial crops (cotton, sisal).	0.5	Fish	403	-
Dir Beni Mellal	Morocco	Béni Mellal-Khénifra provinces	946,642 (2018)	Olives, cereals, pulses, fodder crops, horticultural crops.	5.7	Crop	400	-
Ait Ouallal Bittit / Ait Yazem	Morocco	Meknès – El Hajeb provinces	865,419 (2018)	Vegetables (potatoes, onion), horticultural crops, olives, cereals, pulses.	9.9	Crop	500	500
Mvomero	Tanzania	Mvomero District	421,741 (2022)	Sugarcane, rice, maize, beans and sorghum.	3.1	Crop	504	482
Kilombero	Tanzania	Kilombero District	582,960 (2022)	Sugarcane, rice, aquaculture.	4.3	Crop, fish	423	-

Chebika	Tunisia	Governorate of Kairouan	749,657 (2022)	Vegetables (peppers, tomatoes) and fruit (apricots, almonds and olives)	8.8	Crop	431	-
Fernana	Tunisia	Governorate of Jendouba	404,853 (2022)	Cereals, livestock, fodder, and market gardening	6.9	Crop	500	500
Kamuli	Uganda	Kamuli District	558,500 (2020)	Maize, sweet potatoes, beans, tomatoes, cassava, soybeans, bananas and groundnuts.	1.0	Crop	400	-
Nakaseke	Uganda	Nakaseke District	234,600 (2020)	Beans, cassava, maize, coffee, bananas, fruits (mangoes, Pineapples, oranges) and vegetables (tomatoes and cabbages)	2.0	Crop	400	-
Kajjansi/Masaka	Uganda	Wakiso, Mukono, Lwengo, Masaka Kamuli and Nagaseke Districts ^b	3,850,164 (2014) ^b	Smallholder fish farming (Nile Tilapia and African catfish), coffee, Matooke, sweet potatoes, pineapples, tomatoes	1.4 ^b	Fish	508	406

^a The population figure is available only for the larger macro administrative level.

^b The Kajjansi/Masaka food hub comprises a territory which spans over six districts given that the focus there was on fish farming. The population data shown is the sum of the population data of all six districts at year 2014. The average farm size is instead the average of the individual districts' sizes.

3 3.1.1 Kenya

4 The three food hubs in Kenya are Mukurweini, Kitui, and Kisumu. The Mukurweini food hub is
5 located in the central part of Kenya and administratively is a sub-county of Nyeri county. The Kitui
6 food hub is located in the Eastern drylands of Kenya, and is a sub-county of Kitui county. The
7 Kisumu food hub is located in the western part of Kenya, in the Lake Victoria basin, and is a sub-
8 county of the Kisumu county where farmers practice fish capture and fish farming. The main food
9 crops grown and sold in the three food hubs include cereals such as maize, sorghum, and millets;
10 pulses such as green grams, cowpeas and pigeon peas; root crops such as cassava, sweet and
11 Irish potatoes and arrow roots; industrial crops such as coffee, cotton, sisal and sunflower; and
12 horticultural crops represented mainly by fruits such as mangoes, pawpaw, and watermelons as
13 well as vegetables such as tomatoes, kales, onions and bullet chilies.

14 3.1.2 Morocco

15 Two major agricultural regions in Morocco have been selected, the Meknès - Fès region and the
16 Beni Mellal - Khénifra region. The Fès - Meknès region, located in the centre-north of Morocco,
17 and more specifically the Meknès - El Hajeb food area, which dominates the Saïs plain, is char-
18 acterised by market vegetables crops (potatoes and onions, etc.) based on drip irrigation, in ad-
19 dition to dry crops (cereals, olives and fodder). The area has significant agricultural potential, but
20 faces the problem of intensifying agricultural production through the extension and extensive use
21 of irrigation, which poses huge problems for the sustainability of agricultural activities in relation
22 to water scarcity, the effects of climate change (drought), and farmers' failure to control irrigation
23 inputs (over-irrigation) (Benouniche et al., 2014; Molle & Tanouti, 2017)(Benouniche et al., 2014;
24 Molle & Tanouti, 2017).

25 The Beni Mellal - Khénifra region, located in central Morocco, and more specifically the Dir de
26 Beni Mellal area, consists of a narrow strip of fertile land in a transitional position between the
27 plain and the mountains, some twenty kilometres wide to the south-west and narrowing towards
28 the north-east. The area is dominated by olive groves, the region's traditional crop. This is essen-
29 tially subsistence farming, with low levels of farm income. Agriculture is the leading sector in the

30 local economy, employing 42% of the working population. The food hub area covers 137,000 ha,
31 40% of which is used for farming.

32 3.1.3 Tanzania

33 In Tanzania, the study was conducted in the Kilombero and Mvomero food hubs, located in the
34 southern and northern parts of the Morogoro region respectively, spanning a total area of 7,325
35 km². The majority of the residents in the Kilombero District are sugarcane and rice producers. On
36 a small scale, beans, pigeon peas, sweet potatoes, and cow peas are also grown as sources of
37 food and supplemental income. In Mvomero, the cultivation of sugarcane, rice, maize, beans and
38 sorghum is more predominant (Olmos, 2001)(Olmos, 2001). Livestock keeping is done as well by
39 pastoralist communities, especially the Maasai.

40 3.1.4 Tunisia

41 In Tunisia the study was conducted in the Chebika and Fernana food hubs. The delegation of
42 Fernana (governorate of Jendouba) is predominantly rural with limited infrastructures and high
43 unemployment and illiteracy rates. Agriculture is very varied and mainly focused on cereal grow-
44 ing, livestock, fodder, and market gardening. Agricultural land in the delegation is approximately
45 27,400 ha, with an average farm size of 6.9 ha. Small farms (under 10 ha) represent 50% of the
46 surface area and 86% of the number of farms (CRDA Jendouba, 2022). This situation has a
47 significant impact on production yields, and contributes to the high poverty rate of 37% (National
48 Institute of Statistics-World Bank, 2020). Moreover, these factors contribute to the aggravation of
49 the problem of migration of young people to the main Tunisian cities.

50 The delegation of Chebika (governorate of Kairouan) is characterised by subsistence agriculture,
51 dominant rural environment, weakness at the level of basic infrastructure, high unemployment
52 rate, high illiteracy rate, very low levels of education, a significant rural exodus and a high poverty
53 rate of 35% (National Institute of Statistics-World Bank, 2020)(National Institute of Statistics-
54 World Bank, 2020). Agriculture is the primary economic sector for the local economy, employing

55 30% of the active population. The agricultural area covers 46,178 ha. The governorate of Kairouan is best known for its production of vegetables (peppers, tomatoes) and fruit (apricots, almonds, and olives). In fact, it is the country's leading producer of chillies with almost 95,000 tonnes in 2020, as well as apricots with over 15,000 tonnes³.

59 3.1.5 Uganda

60 In Uganda, data were collected from three food hubs located in six districts, and mostly from
61 Kamuli, Nakaseke, and Masaka. In the Kamuli district, agriculture is the main source of livelihood.
62 About 93% of the households are engaged in agriculture and a great percentage (78%) largely
63 depend on subsistence farming as their source of livelihood (Uganda Bureau of Statistics,
64 2014)(Uganda Bureau of Statistics, 2014). Maize, sweet potatoes, beans, tomatoes, cassava,
65 soybeans, bananas, and groundnuts are the commonly grown crops for home consumption,
66 whereas cash crops are dominated by sugarcane and robusta coffee. Farmers also make use of
67 seasonal wetlands to grow rice and vegetables. Agriculture in the district is affected by declining
68 soil fertility, crop and livestock pests and diseases, prolonged drought, counterfeit inputs on the
69 market, and poor post-harvest handling and storage. The district has high poverty and illiteracy
70 rates that have limited investments in businesses. In turn, the Masaka district is endowed with
71 loamy soils and receives a favourable amount of rain throughout the year that is conducive for
72 agriculture. About, 67% of the population is employed in the agricultural sector (Uganda Bureau
73 of Statistics, 2014)(Uganda Bureau of Statistics, 2014). The district used to be referred to as the
74 food basket of the Ugandan central region; however, the agricultural sector has suffered the ef-
75 fects of climate change and declining soil fertility that has resulted into low productivity.

76 For the past 20 years, smallholder fish farming in the districts within the Kajjansi-Masaka food
77 hub has gained popularity among households as an alternative source of income. The most grown
78 species are the Nile tilapia and African catfish. Though, fish predators such as snakes, high cost

³ Data obtained from the Kairouan regional commission for agricultural development.

79 of feed, the lack of capital, and theft of fish have been highlighted as major constraints to the
80 enterprises (Atukunda et al., 2018; Hyuha et al., 2011)(Atukunda et al., 2018; Hyuha et al., 2011).

81 Lastly, Nakaseke district is mainly occupied by pastoralists although it has two agro-ecological
82 zones: the northern pastoral zone dominated by cattle keepers (making up more than three quar-
83 ters of the land) and the southern crop-based one that is characterised by crop growing. Other
84 major economic activities in the district include charcoal burning, brick making, and sand mining.
85 In recent years, the district has attracted investors in the established industrial park in Kapeeka
86 town. The growing number of industries in the park has not only created jobs for the locals but
87 also provided agri-processing services to farmers, especially fruit farmers that were previously
88 experiencing high post-harvest losses.

89 3.2 Survey and experimental design and administration

90 In this study, we use data from both the standardised questionnaire and the lab-in-the-field ex-
91 periments. The questionnaire comprised 36 questions and was delivered in all the 12 study areas
92 to investigate smallholder farmers' habits and conditions, levels of trust, (stated) propensity to
93 innovate, risk perception, experiences, and demographic as well as contextual factors (Reference
94 omitted for peer review)⁴. The questionnaire was drafted in English, translated into local lan-
95 guages, back translated for consistency checks, and pilot-tested with students and then farmers.

96 The behavioural experiments, which were run in five of the 12 abovementioned study areas, con-
97 sisted of three incentive-compatible games presented in a fixed order (to reduce complexity for
98 the enumerators): (i) a two-round public good game with country-specific treatments; (ii) a lottery
99 game to elicit risk preferences (from Holt and Laury, 2022); and finally, (iii) a task to elicit time
100 preferences. Only the latter two are used in this study.

101 Farmers were invited to the locality where the survey and the experimental sessions were organ-
102 ised. Each session included about 20 participants (to create groups for performing the public good

⁴ Three of the 12 food hubs involved smallholder farmers producing fish (aquaculture). These are: Kil-
ombero (Tanzania), where nevertheless fish farmers constitute a small subset of the sample, Kisumu
(Kenya), and Kajjansi-Masaka (Uganda). Some of the survey questions were adapted to their different
contexts.

103 game) and lasted for around three hours including the filling in of the questionnaire. Participants'
104 responses to the questionnaire and choices in the behavioural experiments were recorded using
105 pen and paper, except in Morocco and Tanzania, where data collection was implemented using
106 tablets. Local enumerators provided one-to-one support to farmers to complete the required
107 tasks. During the behavioural experiments, stakes were expressed in experimental tokens, and
108 banknotes with the brand of the project reporting the values in tokens were used for the public
109 good game. After the instruction of each game were read out loud, participants had the chance to
110 ask questions to the enumerators.

111 *Risk preferences.* Risk preferences were elicited through a multiple price elicitation task (Holt and
112 Laury, 2022). Each participant had to make 10 choices between pairs of lotteries with varying
113 odds of winning the higher stake (Lottery B was riskier than Lottery A, i.e., the difference between
114 the stakes was larger). In both lotteries, the odds of winning the higher stake increased for each
115 choice (from 0.1 to 1.0).

116 *Time preferences.* Time preferences were elicited using a Multiple Price List (Andersen et al.,
117 2008)(Andersen et al., 2008). Each participant had to make 10 choices between two options.
118 Option A paid 100 tokens two weeks after the end of the experiment, while Option B paid a larger
119 amount after four weeks⁵. The amount paid in Option B increased by around 6% from one choice
120 to the other, ranging from 105 to 166 tokens. After the end of the game, participants were asked
121 to respond to two additional control questions. (Kuhfuss et al., 2022)

122 At the end of the experimental session, the participants received a show up fee and a payoff that
123 depended on the results of the games. Participant farmers were also paid travel costs and pro-
124 vided refreshments. During the experimental sessions, the payoffs were expressed in tokens, and
125 converted into local currencies at the end of the overall session using a rate (communicated at
126 the start of the session) that ensured the same average payoff at purchasing power parity across

⁵ We used 2 and 4 weeks rather than 0 and 2 because otherwise the choices would also be driven by transaction costs and trust towards the experimenters who should provide the payments. With 2 and 4, the choices should only be determined by the farmers' time preferences, since these two elements are constant across Options A and B.

127 the five countries. More precisely, the average total payoff, inclusive of the show up fee, was set
128 as equal to 1.5 times the daily agricultural wage in the region.⁶ To avoid spill-over effects, the
129 extractions to calculate the payoffs in the risk and time preference games were implemented at
130 the end of the full session, and the farmers were paid privately in a separate room and asked to
131 leave the venue immediately afterwards. The payoff of the time preference game was transferred
132 by phone (or paid in cash, where that option was not available) after two or four weeks. The
133 average actual payments for the risk and time elicitation games in each country are presented in
134 Appendix A, and range, in total, between 226 tokens for Morocco and 260 tokens for Tunisia. The
135 experimental and survey protocols including procedures, instructions for researchers and enu-
136 merators, and logistic aspects were archived in Zenodo (Reference omitted for peer review).

137 Prior to fieldwork, ethical clearance was obtained both from the Bioethics Committee of the insti-
138 tution leading the project, and from the ethics committees of the institutions coordinating fieldwork
139 in the single countries. A consent form (in the local language of each food hub) was used to gather
140 the consent of the participants to take part in the experimental and survey activities. Local enu-
141 merators ensured that each participant understood the aforementioned information to make an
142 informed decision. No sensitive personal data were collected.

143 In total, 2,393 participants took part in the experimental sessions, of which 52 did not respond to
144 the survey questionnaire. Therefore, the final sample considered for the analysis presented in
145 Section 4.3, which combines both survey and experimental data, includes 2,341 observations.⁷

⁶ Before fieldwork, we calculated the theoretical maximum and minimum earning in a session: between 5 and 190 tokens in the risk preferences game; between 100 and 166 in the time preferences game; between 0-30 and 300-460 tokens (different countries were assigned different treatments) in each round of the public good game; and 100 tokens as a show-up fee. The average between the minimum and maximum was set equal to 1.5 times the agricultural wage to obtain the conversion rate.

⁷ With such sample size, given a 0.50 baseline proportion, the minimum effect detectable in a one-proportion test with an acceptable power of 0.80, a significance level of 0.05, and a confidence interval of 0.95, is 0.0289. Since some observations are lost for various reasons, the minimum detectable effect given these parameters can be slightly lower, as specified in the following.

146 4. Data and descriptive statistics

147 In this section, we describe our outcome of interest (4.1), and the explanatory variables (4.2) used
148 in this study. We then present a series of summary statistics, with a specific overview on the
149 setbacks experienced by farmers within each of the studied African countries (4.3).

150 4.1 Outcome variables

151 The aim of this research is to assess the relationship between smallholder farmers' aversive expe-
152 riences and their time preferences. The primary outcome of interest is thus the farmers' patience
153 levels, elicited through the time preferences game. These patience levels are expressed both in
154 terms of a threshold (hereafter, the switch point) and as a discount rate, estimated jointly with risk
155 preferences using maximum likelihood estimators à la Andersen et al. (2008). These different
156 estimates of our outcome variable are subsequently utilised in Section 5 in two complementary
157 approaches to examine their association with farmers' adverse experiences.

158 **Switch point.** The switch point is the point at which a participant switches their preference be-
159 tween the smaller, sooner reward and the larger, later rewards (or between different risky choices
160 in a risk context). In our time preference game, this is represented by the choice (out of 10) at
161 which farmers switch to the option entailing waiting for 2 more weeks (Option B) in exchange for
162 a higher payment. Evaluating switch point patterns across participants can provide useful infor-
163 mation about their patience levels and overall decision-making behaviour (Bigoni et al., 2022).
164 Yet scholars working on time preferences suggest more comprehensive analyses which can con-
165 sider jointly time preferences and risk preferences (see, for instance, the seminal work of Ander-
166 sen et al., 2008). Indeed, relying only on the switching behaviour in a single experiment does not
167 allow to separate the influences of risk preferences (aversion to risk) from time preferences (im-
168 patience or discounting the future). We measure farmers' patience at individual level on a 0 to 10
169 patience score, with 0 indicating farmers with highest levels of impatience, whereas 10 indicates

170 the highest levels of patience.⁸ We use this variable, along with a series of explanatory variables
171 described in the following section, to run a first model assessing the associations between small-
172 holder farmers' attitudes and patience level. Results are reported in 5.1. In this initial analysis, the
173 farmers making inconsistent choices (i.e., switching more than once between Options A and B)
174 were removed from the sample (=403). These account for 17% of the initial sample, leaving a
175 final sample of 1,938 farmers.⁹

176 **Structural estimation.** We then model risk and temporal preferences jointly, using Maximum
177 Likelihood Estimation (MLE) à la Andersen et al. (2008). In this analysis, we rely on binary choices
178 made by the farmers between sooner and later amounts to estimate structurally the discount rate
179 δ of our study sample. We then introduce a series of covariates to account for heterogeneity in
180 risk and time preferences. This procedure enables us to retain in our analysis the participants
181 with multiple switch points, which need not be excluded during the estimation. Results and esti-
182 mation strategy are reported in 5.2.

183 4.2 Explanatory variables

184 The explanatory variables are 10 environmental, social, and economic setbacks that individual
185 smallholder farmers experienced during the year prior to the sampling date. Farmers were asked
186 to assess, using a 1-5 Likert scale, to what extent they experienced the setbacks, which are pre-
187 sented in Table 2 (*Did you experience any of the following setbacks during the last year?*). Set-
188 backs were retrieved from Kijima (2019), and adapted to the context-specific situation of the stud-
189 ied areas (i.e., crop versus fish farmers). We aggregated the setbacks into the three social, eco-
190 nomic, and environmental macro classes presented in Table 2 using the arithmetic mean and
191 rounded to the nearest integer¹⁰. These 1-5 scales were used to generate dummies for each

⁸ Therefore, the switch point can be also defined as the count of the number of times a farmer selection Option B out of 10 choices.

⁹ With such sample size, the minimum effect detectable in a one-proportion test increases slightly to 0.0318.

¹⁰ Other dimensionality reduction techniques such as PCA and CFA were employed, but they proved ineffective in identifying a reduced number of factors that could explain a significant share of the variance.

192 macro class measuring whether a farmer experienced social, economic, and environmental set-
 193 backs to any extent, as opposed to not experiencing it, on average. Following the literature ex-
 194 plored in Section 2, we expect that farmers who have experienced adverse social, environmental,
 195 and economic events are more likely to be impatient (Cassar et al., 2017), thus opting for smaller
 196 yet close-to-certain agricultural rewards rather than larger and uncertain rewards in the future.

197 **Table 2.** List of setbacks identified, mean values, and standard deviations (N=2,341).

Setbacks	Category	Mean	Standard deviation
Social setbacks (aggregate)	-	2.40	1.07
Food shortage	Social	2.91	1.63
Health	Social	2.72	1.55
Social problems (violence or crime)	Social	1.63	1.27
Environmental setbacks (aggregate)	-	2.39	0.98
Drought	Environmental	2.68	1.63
Flood	Environmental	1.52	1.15
Pest infestation	Environmental	3.03	1.63
Economic setbacks (aggregate)		2.68	0.94
Dispossession	Economic	1.48	1.14
Cost increase (price of fertilizer and seed)	Economic	3.70	1.52
Job loss	Economic	2.00	1.51
Income reduction	Economic	3.48	1.52

198 Beside the three abovementioned variables of interest, we include in our models a series of ex-
 199 planatory factors that are expected to be related to farmers' time preferences. These includes:

- 200 1. *Farmer's worries about the future.* We include the measurements of a series of worries
 201 (framed similarly to the setbacks) that farmers expect to experience in their near future
 202 (*Regarding your near future, are you worried about any of the reasons below?*). We ex-
 203 pect that farmers having higher future economic, social, and/or environmental worries are

204 more likely to modify their agricultural practices potentially affected by future adverse ex-
205periences. Worries about the future were aggregated like the setbacks in three macro
206classes (social, economic, and environmental) through their arithmetic mean. These were
207then turned into binary variables, structured in the same way as for setbacks.

208 2. *Farmer's stated preferences towards innovation, risk, and trust.* We include in our esti-
209mation three measures of the farmers' own perception of risk, their trust towards agricul-
210tural organisations, and their state openness to agricultural innovation. These traits were
211measured on a 1-5 agreement scale ranging from complete disagreement (1) to complete
212agreement (5). For all questions, the highest level corresponds to farmer profiles with the
213highest openness to innovation, risk aversion, and highest trust towards organisation pro-
214moting innovation in agriculture. From these variables we generated dummies that indi-
215cate the farmer's overall agreement or disagreement concerning stated preferences on
216risk, trust, and innovation. We expect that higher levels of patience are associated with
217risk-tolerant profiles, higher willingness to uptake agricultural innovations, and more trust
218towards value chain organizations.

219 3. *Measurement of the farmer's revealed preferences on risk.* To consider the interlinks be-
220tween risk and time preferences, in our first analysis (Section 5.1) we include a measure-
221ment of the farmers' revealed preferences on risk, elicited through the risk preference
222game (Section 3.2). Farmers' attitudes to risk are measured using a 1 to 10 score, with 1
223showing a high willingness to take risks (risk-takers) and 10 a low willingness to take risks
224(risk-averse profiles). These scores correspond to the switch point at which farmers start
225choosing the high-stake lottery in the series of 10 choices, rather than the low-stake lot-
226tery or, equally, the count of how many times a farmer chose Lottery A, out of 10. Similar
227to time preferences, farmers making inconsistent choices of risk were removed when
228running this additional specification of the Poisson regression (inconsistent responses to
229the risk preference game = 1,112; 47.5% of the sample). Instead, in MLE analyses re-
230ported in 5.2, risk preferences were structurally estimated jointly with time preferences

231 through a MLE estimation. Based on what said in point 2, we expect to find a significant
232 and positive association between patience and risk aversion.

233 4. *Socio-demographic and farm production variables.* We finally included a set of controls
234 expected to have an impact on the individual farmer's patience levels. These are: the
235 farmer's age, level of education (illiterate, literate with no qualifications, and literate with
236 qualifications), gender, share of household income spent on food purchases (above or
237 below 50%), and land/pond total size.¹¹

238 4.3 Descriptive statistics

239 In Table 3, we report descriptive statistics for the outcome and explanatory variables. Significant
240 differences were found when comparing variables amongst countries. This shows the high degree
241 of heterogeneity that exists across different countries when evaluating farmers' worries, dis-
242 tresses, and stated or revealed preferences. In our models, we controlled for this heterogeneity
243 through country-fixed effects.

244 As a preliminary check, correlation tests between the explanatory variables and the farmers' pa-
245 tience levels measured through the switch point are given in Table 4. The highest significant
246 correlations were found with social and environmental setbacks (8% and 7% respectively), literate
247 farmers with no qualification (9%) and female farmers (14%). Regarding farmers' preferences,
248 we found negative correlation between patience levels and neutral (stated) trust preferences (8%)
249 as well as negative correlation with farmers revealed (experimental) risk preferences (12%). Alt-
250 hough significant, all these correlation coefficients are all very small.

¹¹ In the three food hubs where the sample is made of smallholder farmers producing fish (aquaculture), the farm size was not assessed in hectares, but as the total size (in m²) of the farmer's ponds/tanks/cages. To facilitate uniform analysis across different measurement scales, we implemented Min-Max normalization, creating a new continuous variable that standardizes the original distributions of land or production system sizes to a range between 0 and 1.

251 **Table 3.** Descriptive statistics by country - outcome and explanatory variables.

Variable	Mean (overall)	Mean (KE)	Mean (MA)	Mean (TN)	Mean (TZ)	Mean (UG)	ANOVA test (F value)
Patience level (switch point)	6.80	7.80 ^a	5.44	7.10	7.64 ^a	6.34	33.12***
Social setbacks	0.78	0.76	0.67	0.82 ^a	0.82 ^a	0.83 ^a	13.22***
Economic setbacks	0.93	0.91 ^{a,b}	0.92 ^b	0.99	0.88 ^a	0.93 ^b	11.19***
Environmental setbacks	0.83	0.89 ^a	0.74	0.87 ^a	0.95	0.66	46.65***
Social worries	0.83	0.82 ^b	0.77 ^a	0.89 ^c	0.81 ^{a,b}	0.88 ^c	8.71***
Economic worries	0.91	0.89	0.93 ^a	0.98	0.83	0.93 ^a	21.01***
Environmental worries	0.85	0.87 ^b	0.80 ^a	0.93	0.88 ^b	0.76 ^a	14.87***
Age (years)	46.40	52.27	48.22	45.51 ^a	41.14	43.83 ^a	41.80***
Education (illiterate =1)	0.18	0.04 ^a	0.36	0.29	0.12	0.05 ^a	79.36***
Education (literate, no qualification =1)	0.11	0.29	0.00	0.06 ^a	0.11	0.06 ^a	68.71***
Education (literate with qualification =1)	0.71	0.68 ^a	0.63 ^a	0.65 ^a	0.77	0.89	23.88***
Gender (female = 1)	0.35	0.43 ^a	0.14	0.47 ^a	0.42 ^a	0.30	40.50***
Income spent on food	0.57	0.48	0.59 ^a	0.75	0.62 ^a	0.32	46.94***
Land/Pond size (Min-Max transformation)	0.008	0.00002 ^a	0.0002 ^a	0.0001 ^a	0.00004 ^a	0.050	127.40***
Farmer's risk aversion (low=1)	0.38	0.19	0.48	0.71	0.11	0.38	149.06***

Farmer's risk aversion (neutral=1)	0.09	0.09 ^a	0.13	0.08 ^a	0.08 ^a	0.07 ^a	3.00***
Farmer's risk aversion (high=1)	0.53	0.72	0.39	0.21	0.81	0.56	148.12***
Farmer's trust (low=1)	0.15	0.18 ^{c,d}	0.21 ^d	0.15 ^{b,c}	0.09 ^a	0.12 ^{a,b}	8.23***
Farmer's trust (neutral =1)	0.11	0.10 ^a	0.11 ^{a,b}	0.14 ^b	0.10 ^a	0.09 ^a	1.87***
Farmer's trust (high =1)	0.74	0.72 ^a	0.68 ^a	0.71 ^a	0.81 ^b	0.79 ^b	7.51***
Farmer's innovation (low=1)	0.09	0.10 ^c	0.05 ^{a,b}	0.17	0.08 ^{b,c}	0.03 ^a	15.40***
Farmer's innovation (neutral =1)	0.04	0.02 ^a	0.05 ^b	0.04 ^{a,b}	0.04 ^{a,b}	0.03 ^a	1.90*
Farmer's innovation (high =1)	0.87	0.88 ^a	0.89 ^a	0.79	0.89	0.94 ^a	11.55***
Risk aversion level (switch point)	5.50	2.78	6.01 ^a	5.29	5.98 ^a	3.89	36.83***

KE= Kenya, MA= Morocco, TZ = Tanzania, TN= Tunisia, UG= Uganda; *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1. Superscript letters indicate groups that do not differ significantly.

252

253

Table 4. Pearson's correlation tests between the time preference switch point and the explanatory variables.

Explanatory variable	Pearson's correlation coefficient	p value
Social setbacks	0.08	<0.001
Economic setbacks	0.03	0.029
Environmental setbacks	0.07	<0.001
Social worries	0.04	<0.001

Economic worries	-0.03	<0.001
Environmental worries	0.05	<0.001
<hr/>		
Age (years)	0.02	0.005
Education (illiterate =1)	-0.04	<0.001
Education (literate, no qualification =1)	0.09	<0.001
Education (literate with qualification =1)	-0.03	<0.001
Gender (female = 1)	0.14	<0.001
Income spent on food	0.02	0.003
Land/Pond size	-0.04	0.000
<hr/>		
Farmer's risk aversion (low=1)	-0.03	<0.001
Farmer's risk aversion (neutral=1)	-0.01	1.0
Farmer's risk aversion (high=1)	0.03	<0.001
Farmer's trust (low=1)	-0.03	<0.001
Farmer's trust (neutral =1)	-0.08	1.0
Farmer's trust (high =1)	0.03	<0.001
Farmer's innovation (low=1)	0.00	1.0
Farmer's innovation (neutral =1)	-0.01	1.0
Farmer's innovation (high =1)	0.00	1.0
<hr/>		
Risk aversion level	-0.12	<0.001
<hr/>		

255 **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** shows how common the setbacks are among
 256 smallholder crop and fish farmers in our five country samples. The three highest rated concerns
 257 are: (i) the shortage/quality/cost of available inputs – fingerlings (fish farmers), pesticides and
 258 seed feeds (crop farmers); (ii) income reduction; and (iii) pest infestation, with average values of
 259 3.7, 3.5, and 3.0, respectively, on the original 1-5 scale. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the
 260 ongoing disruption of supply chains, farmers in Africa, particularly those cultivating irrigated crops,
 261 experienced a sharp rise in the cost of imported inputs such as potassium fertilizers, seeds, plant
 262 protection products, and agricultural equipment (Nchanji et al., 2021). This increase in production
 263 costs intensified concerns among farmers regarding their incomes and profit margins
 264 (Ibid). (Nchanji et al., 2021) This explains the importance of these two economic setbacks for
 265 smallholder local farmers.

266

267 **Figure 2.** Setbacks experienced by farmers during the previous year in each studied country.

268 Self-evaluation reported on a 1-5 Likert scale.

269 When looking at individual countries, variations in the relevance of the experienced setbacks can
270 be observed. Despite the increase in the price of farm inputs is a shared concern across countries,
271 other country-based issues emerge as relevant. In Kenya and Tunisia, food shortage scores an
272 average of 3.1 and 3.5 respectively on a 1-5 scale. This is probably due to severe drought result-
273 ing from four consecutive failure of rainy seasons, leading to millions of people in the country
274 facing hunger and thirst. High inflation, climate-related disasters, conflicts and displacement are
275 additional local and global challenges impacting food shortages in rural Kenya.

276 In Morocco and Tunisia, the highest scores were for drought and increasing input costs. Currently,
277 and since 2021, Morocco has been hit by the worst droughts in history, a consequence of climate
278 change and inefficient water management. According to data from the Ministry of Equipment and
279 Water (DGM, 2023), drought is set to become progressively more severe in Morocco until 2050
280 as a result of falling rainfall and rising temperatures. In particular, the 2021-2022 agricultural sea-
281 son was the driest in the last 40 years at least. It has been marked by extreme drought, accom-
282 panied by exceptionally high temperatures, especially during the critical phases of the cereal cy-
283 cle. This is the most important factor explaining farmers' setbacks in relation to reduced rainfall
284 and increased risks to the availability of water for irrigated crops, in addition to the increased costs
285 associated with irrigation.

286 In Tunisia, the effects of rising input and fuel prices, combined with stagnating farm-gate prices,
287 are being felt most by smallholder farmers, the vast majority of whom are heavily in debt. As a
288 consequence, many smallholder farmers are reducing the area they sow. Rising prices for agri-
289 cultural raw materials are also having a severe impact on livestock production, which is suffering
290 from the combined effects of drought, forage shortages and rising feed prices, leading to a decline
291 in livestock numbers in recent years (Gana, 2023).(Gana, 2023).

292 In Tanzania, farmers are particularly worried about pest infestations. This is a common concern
293 for Tanzanian farmers, already highlighted in the survey conducted by Pallangyo et al., (2019)Pal-
294 langyo et al., (2019), where they show that crop pests and diseases are a major constraint to crop
295 production in rural Tanzania.

296 Finally Ugandan farmers were mostly affected by increase in costs, reduction in income, and
297 health problems. The former two can be attributed to increase in not only counterfeit seed and
298 fertilizer but also their prices, and yet these are some of the most significant driving factors for
299 optimum production. Increased input prices contribute to higher farm expenditures whilst reduced
300 harvests owing to other factors such as weather and pest infestation result in less entries, conse-
301 quently reducing farm income. The importance of health setbacks to farmers in Uganda is prob-
302 ably linked to farm labour dynamics and produce marketing. Data collection was carried out amid
303 the COVID-19 pandemic, during which farmers had experienced labour shortages. Therefore,
304 some farmers either did not carry out some production activities or did with difficulty. Ugandan
305 farmers also faced post-harvest losses due to their inability to sell their products because of dis-
306 ruptions of the local food value chains.

307 **5. Empirical analysis**

308 In this section, we present the model and estimation strategies used to evaluate the associations
309 between smallholder farmers' individual characteristics, past experiences, and their time prefer-
310 ences. First, we analyse the relationship between smallholder farmers' attitudes and their time
311 preferences, measured using the switch point, by estimating a Quasi-MLE Poisson model, and
312 report on the main results (Section 5.1). In Section 5.2, we detail the results obtained by applying
313 the approach developed by Andersen et al. (2008) to jointly estimate farmers' time and risk pref-
314 erences, and incorporating our explanatory variables into the estimation of the discount rate.

315 **5.1 Farmers' patience levels and adverse event**

316 **Model.** In this initial analysis, we estimated the association between smallholder farmers' attitudes
317 and their patience level. We employed a Quasi-MLE Poisson model to accommodate the count

318 data structure of our outcome variable, adjusting standard errors to account for overdispersion¹².
 319 We also accounted for the boundary at the upper limit of the switch point. We treated this as an
 320 upper corner solution, given that the clustering of switch points at 10 represents a conscious,
 321 utility-maximizing decision, where farmers consistently prefer the delayed but larger reward (Op-
 322 tion B)¹³.

323 Our empirical equation reads as follows:

$$324 \quad E[Y_{i(c,s)}] = \exp(\alpha + S'_{i(c,s)}\beta + W'_{i(c,s)}\gamma + X'_{i(c,s)}\delta + P'_{i(c,s)}\vartheta + \mu \text{risk}_{i(c,s)} + \rho_c + \partial_{s(c)}) + \epsilon_{i(c,s)}, \quad (\text{eq.1})$$

325 Where $E[Y_{i(c,s)}]$ is the expected switch point of the i^{th} farmer's time preferences from country c
 326 and experimental session s , measured on a 0 to 10 patience level (Section 4.1). The regressors
 327 of interest are farmer experienced social, economic, and environmental setbacks ($S'_{i(c,s)}$). The
 328 model also considers social, economic, and environmental worries towards the future ($W'_{i(c,s)}$), a
 329 series of socio-demographic controls $X'_{i(c,s)}$ (farmer's age, education, gender, income spent on
 330 food purchases, and land/pond total size), farmer's stated preferences towards innovation, risk,
 331 and trust ($P'_{i(c,s)}$), as well as a measurement of the farmer's revealed preferences on risk
 332 ($\text{risk}_{i(c,s)}$). We include this latter element to assess the association between temporal and risk
 333 preferences of the study participants. Finally, we include country fixed effects (ρ_c) and experi-
 334 mental session fixed effects ($\partial_{s(c)}$) to control for time-invariant country- and session-specific het-
 335 erogeneity. All models were tested for multicollinearity, with diagnostic results indicating no evi-
 336 dence of multicollinearity among the main independent variables.

337 Based on Eq.1, four complementary specifications were estimated. The first two specifications
 338 include only social, economic, and environmental setbacks ($S'_{i(c,s)}$) and worries ($W'_{i(c,s)}$), with the

¹² The model goodness-of-fit was assessed using the deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics. The deviance statistic for a Poisson regression was 2599.19, p-value <0.001, and the Pearson Chi-Square statistic was 1751.64, p-value <0.001. This indicated evidence of poor fit leading to the selection of a Quasi-MLE Poisson model.

¹³ The distribution of the outcome variable at country and cross-country level are provided in Appendix C.

339 latter one including country fixed effects. The third specification adds the socio-demographic con-
 340 trols $X'_{i(c,s)}$ farmer's stated preferences towards innovation, risk, and trust ($P'_{i(c,s)}$) and information
 341 from the behavioural risk preference experiment ($risk_{i(c,s)}$) to the estimation. The fourth one in-
 342 cludes experimental session fixed effects (∂_s). We refer to this latter specification as our baseline
 343 model. Given that this analysis relies on consistent switching patterns, farmers exhibiting incon-
 344 sistent responses to either the time and risk elicitation games were removed from the sample.

345 **Results.** Table 5 reports the estimated incident rate ratios (IRRs) from the Poisson regression
 346 models. In all specifications, the results show a positive and statistically significant effect of expe-
 347 rienced social setbacks on farmers' time preferences, suggesting that experiencing social set-
 348 backs is associated to higher patience. In the last two specifications, we also observe a significant
 349 and negative effect of economic worries on farmers' time preferences, suggesting that these wor-
 350 ries lead to less patience.

351 Using the estimates from the most comprehensive specification (d), we observe that farmers who
 352 have experienced adverse social setbacks exhibit a 15% higher rate of patience, *ceteris paribus*,
 353 while farmers who express greater concerns about future economic conditions are exhibit a 17%
 354 lower in patience, *ceteris paribus*. Finally, with each unit increase in farmers' risk aversion, as
 355 measured though the experimental lottery, the expected rate of patience decreases by 2.7%.
 356 Farmers' gender and perceived trust in the agricultural value chain organizations also contribute
 357 to predicting farmers' time preferences. In particular, female farmers and farmers with higher self-
 358 reported trust in agricultural value chain organizations are, on average, more patient, respectively
 359 by 14.8% and 12%.

360 **Table 5.** Estimated effects on farmers' patience (Poisson model incident rates with robust SE in
 361 parentheses).

Variable	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
Social setbacks	1.141*** (0.049)	1.101** (0.048)	1.151*** (0.058)	1.151*** (0.060)

Economic setbacks	1.047 (0.069)	1.054 (0.071)	1.050 (0.085)	1.047 (0.084)
Environmental setbacks	1.076* (0.048)	0.973 (0.044)	0.940 (0.052)	0.968 (0.055)
Social worries	0.978 (0.048)	1.000 (0.050)	0.921 (0.053)	0.910 (0.053)
Economic worries	0.833*** (0.052)	0.900* (0.057)	0.824** (0.064)	0.830** (0.064)
Environmental worries	1.078 (0.055)	1.066 (0.054)	1.097 (0.066)	1.088 (0.066)
Age (years)			1.000 (0.001)	0.999 (0.001)
Education: literate, no qualification			1.135 (0.097)	1.141 (0.103)
Education: literate with qualification			0.989 (0.042)	1.000 (0.044)
Gender (female = 1)			1.153*** (0.048)	1.148*** (0.053)
Income spent on food			0.983 (0.038)	1.002 (0.041)
Land/Pond size			2.705* (1.529)	2.605 (1.570)
Farmer's risk aversion (low)			1.078 (0.071)	1.059 (0.070)
Farmer's risk aversion (high)			1.010 (0.067)	1.002 (0.067)
Farmer's trust (low)			1.071 (0.075)	1.021 (0.072)
Farmer's trust (high)			1.126** (0.066)	1.120* (0.066)
Farmer's innovation (low)			1.035 (0.100)	1.046 (0.104)
Farmer's innovation (high)			0.968 (0.078)	0.955 (0.078)
Risk aversion level			0.974*** (0.008)	0.973*** (0.008)
Country FE	NO	YES	YES	YES

Session FE	NO	NO	NO	YES
Observations	1,938	1,938	1,181	1,181
McFadden's pseudo R ²	0.129	0.161	0.523	0.533
Robust standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1				

362

363 In Appendix B, we present the results of alternative specifications using Tobit models, which sim-
364 ilarly account for the corner solution structure of our data. The results are similar to the Poisson
365 model estimates.

366 5.2 Joint estimation of risk and time preferences

367 **Model.** We followed Andersen et al. (2008) by modelling risk and time preferences jointly through
368 a MLE approach. The log-likelihood equation, maximised using standard numerical methods, was
369 formulated as follows (the explicit derivation as in Andersen et al. (2008) is omitted for brevity):

$$\begin{aligned}
370 \quad \ln L(r, \delta, \mu, \nu; y, \omega, \lambda, X) = & \sum_j ((\ln(\nabla EU)|y_j^{RP} = 1) + \ln(1 - \nabla EU)|y_j^{RP} = -1) \\
371 & + \sum_j ((\ln(\nabla PV)|y_j^{TP} = 1) + \ln(1 - \nabla PV)|y_j^{TP} = -1)^{14}, \quad (\text{eq.2})
\end{aligned}$$

372 Where $y_j^{RP} = 1$ (-1) corresponds to selecting Option B (A) in choice j of the risk preference (RP)
373 task, while $y_j^{TP} = 1$ (-1) denotes the choice of Option B (A) in the time preference (TP) task j ¹⁵.
374 Risk and time preferences were estimated using a constant relative risk aversion (CRRA) speci-
375 fication (Holt & Laury, 2002) based on the Expected Utility (EU) for each lottery pair in the risk

¹⁴ Differently from Andersen et al. (2008), our model does not assume responses that reflect indifference.

¹⁵ As in Andersen et al. (2008), we apply a clustering procedure to account for panel effects arising from unobserved individual heterogeneity. Subsequently, the dataset used for the implementation of the MLE consists of a panel with 46,820 risk aversion and discount rate choices, collected from 2,341 participants.

376 preference task, and the present value (PV) of the utility of the two lottery outcomes in the time
377 preference task¹⁶.

378 Eq.2 indicates that the joint likelihood of risk and discount rate responses depends on the esti-
379 mates of the risk parameter r , the discount rate δ , and their respective noise parameters (μ and
380 ν). With respect to the risk parameter r , $r = 0$ denotes risk neutral behaviour, $r > 0$ indicates risk
381 aversion and finally, $r < 0$ stands for risk-taking behaviour. For the discount rate δ , a higher value
382 corresponds to greater impatience, as individuals assign less importance to delayed rewards
383 compared to immediate ones. Eq.2 also assumes exogenous and time-invariant values of back-
384 ground consumption ω and the periods λ over which the two delayed monetary amounts are
385 integrated with ω . Finally, X represents a vector of farmers' individual characteristics, including
386 farmers' self-evaluation of their exposure to social, economic, and environmental setbacks.

387 To estimate our model, consistently with Andersen et al. (2008) we assume $\lambda = 1$, meaning that
388 the delayed income obtained from each participant from the time preference tasks is integrated
389 with daily background consumption over a single day. The daily background consumption was
390 set equal to 48 tokens, using World Bank data on mean consumption¹⁷.

391 **Results.** Our estimates, excluding individual characteristics, indicate that farmers in our sample
392 are, on average, moderately risk-averse and exhibit a preference for relatively high discount rates

¹⁶ The structure of our experiment involved a short time horizon (i.e., two weeks) to allow for real-life pay-
ments given the timing and budgetary constraints of our project. This time horizon results in exceptionally
low values for both τ and t (as per equations 7' and 8' in Andersen et al. (2008)), which, when estimating
the MLE model, led to an inflation of the estimated discount rate δ . To address this issue, we multiply these
values by a factor of ten. Since our primary focus is on exploring heterogeneity in time preferences relative
to several key variables (especially farmers' setbacks), this adjustment does not affect our main conclusions.

¹⁷ For estimate the daily background consumption ω , we use the value of the World Bank's mean con-
sumption per capita of the bottom 40% of the population (2017 PPP \$ per day), converted into 2021 local
currency units and then into tokens using the conversion rate provided to the participants during the exper-
iments. We use the value for the bottom 40% rather than for the whole population because our exper-
iments are conducted in rural areas that are significantly poorer than the country overall. We also apply a
flat rate 10% reduction of the value since the World Bank aggregate includes the consumption of durable
goods. The resulting omega is the average of this value for the five countries studied. We allow for country
heterogeneity through country dummies. The "Survey mean consumption or income per capita, bottom
40% of population (2017 PPP \$ per day)" was retrieved from [https://data.worldbank.org/indica-
tor/SI.SPR.PCAP](https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SI.SPR.PCAP) ; the "PPP conversion factor, GDP (LCU per international \$)" was retrieved from
<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/PA.NUS.PPP>; the "Inflation, consumer prices (annual %)", used for the
countries whose consumption level pre-dates 2021, was retrieved from [https://data.worldbank.org/indica-
tor/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG](https://data.worldbank.org/indica-
tor/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG).

393 to postpone consumption, reflecting a tendency toward impatience. As reported in Table 6, the
 394 discount rate parameter δ is estimated at 24.6%, which is higher than the rates typically reported
 395 in the literature on time preferences conducted in the lab with students from the Global North
 396 (around 10-15% for Andersen et al., 2008; Aungles & Aidan, 2021; and Ferecatu & Öñçüler,
 397 2016). Given the demographic characteristics of our sample, which comprises rural and often
 398 illiterate farmers, it is unsurprising that the discount rate we found is higher compared to studies
 399 involving university-educated participants. Other studies involving non-university participants
 400 have reported discount rates that are either aligned with or exceed our estimate (Cassar et al.,
 401 2017; Frederick et al., 2002). The risk parameter r at 0.678, is aligned with the literature. The
 402 estimates of the two error terms provide evidence of statistically significant noise in the experi-
 403 ments and are aligned with Andersen et al. (2008), with larger estimates of noise for the risk task
 404 compared to the time preference one (risk preference games are cognitively harder than time
 405 preference tasks).

406 **Table 6.** MLE parameter estimates.

Parameter	Estimate	Robust standard error	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI
Risk parameter r	0.678***	0.054	0.573	0.783
Discount rate δ	0.246***	0.022	0.202	0.289
Noise parameter μ	0.145***	0.023	0.100	0.190
Noise parameter ν	0.033***	0.006	0.020	0.045

Number of observations: 46,820; Number of clusters: 2,341

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

407

408 Table 7 presents the risk and time preference parameters estimated simultaneously with our co-
 409 variates of interest. This approach enables us to assess the relationship between various socio-
 410 demographic descriptors and the discount factor, which is jointly estimated alongside the risk
 411 profile of farmers. The results are consistent with those reported in Section 5.1.

412 We find a significant and negative association between adverse social setbacks and time prefer-
413 ences. Specifically, farmers who have experienced adverse social setbacks exhibit a lower ex-
414 pected discount rate δ , suggesting greater patience (estimate: -0.097; s.e. = 0.053). This effect
415 persists across all MLE specifications reported in Table 7. Contrary to previous findings (e.g.,
416 Chesson & Viscusi, 2000; Ferecatu & Öncüler, 2016), we also identify a significant gender effect,
417 with female farmers displaying higher patience levels compared to their male counterparts (esti-
418 mate: -0.123; s.e. = 0.043). These findings are not universal. For instance, Aungles & Aidan
419 (2021) found that gender plays a role, though with different directionality. Meanwhile, some of the
420 variables found to be significant in Section 5.1, such as future economic conditions and perceived
421 trust, do not show significant effects in the MLE estimates. Finally, the country dummies yield a
422 significant effect, indicating that heterogeneity in time preferences is partly driven by geographical
423 variations (Di Falco & Vieider, 2022).

424 **Table 7.** MLE parameter estimates for the observed heterogeneity model, showing the impact of
425 farmers' individual characteristics on time preferences (robust SE in parentheses).

Variable	Estimates on δ			
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
Social setbacks	-0.144*** (0.052)	-0.115** (0.052)	-0.099* (0.053)	-0.097* (0.053)
Economic setbacks	-0.080 (0.078)	-0.087 (0.081)	-0.092 (0.082)	-0.103 (0.080)
Environmental setbacks	-0.067 (0.057)	0.025 (0.058)	0.028 (0.059)	0.010 (0.059)
Social worries	0.034 (0.061)	0.013 (0.061)	0.028 (0.061)	0.044 (0.060)
Economic worries	0.167** (0.075)	0.112 (0.077)	0.099 (0.078)	0.114 (0.074)
Environmental worries	-0.124* (0.066)	-0.085 (0.066)	-0.086 (0.066)	-0.064 (0.064)
Age (years)			-0.002* (0.001)	-0.002 (0.001)

Education: literate, no qualification			-0.022 (0.082)	-0.051 (0.085)
Education: literate with qualification			0.019 (0.057)	-0.027 (0.058)
Gender (female = 1)			-0.114*** (0.042)	-0.123*** (0.043)
Income spent on food			-0.018 (0.040)	-0.056 (0.041)
Land/Pond size			0.311 (0.570)	0.607 (0.653)
Farmer's risk aversion (low)			-0.001 (0.068)	0.000 (0.069)
Farmer's risk aversion (high)			0.052 (0.067)	0.066 (0.068)
Farmer's trust (low)			-0.028 (0.073)	0.026 (0.073)
Farmer's trust (high)			-0.009 (0.059)	0.004 (0.059)
Farmer's innovation (low)			0.080 (0.110)	0.071 (0.112)
Farmer's innovation (high)			-0.007 (0.091)	0.001 (0.092)
Constant	0.415*** (0.094)	0.276*** (0.099)	0.415** (0.182)	0.492** (0.194)
Country FE	NO	YES	YES	YES
Session FE	NO	NO	NO	YES
Number of observations: 46,820; Number of clusters: 2,341				
Robust standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1				

426

427

6. Conclusions and policy implications

428

In this paper, we assessed how different adverse experiences faced by smallholder African farm-

429

ers are related to their time preferences. We provide empirical evidence of this association by

430

means of variables obtained from surveys as well as in-the-field experiments where we elicit

431 farmers' time preferences by means of standard, incentive-compatible procedures. Our key find-
432 ings is that there is a direct link between the experience of social setbacks and farmers' patience
433 behaviour. Even though our measurement of farmers' setbacks lacked granular temporal detail
434 and was self-reported, linking time preferences to social shocks helped shed lights on the deci-
435 sion-making behaviours African farmers might adopt, representing a significant novelty in the de-
436 bate on time preferences as the relation between farmers' experiences and their patience attitude
437 has not been sufficiently explored to date.

438 Farmers in our sample who have experienced social setbacks during the previous year are more
439 likely to be patient. This finding suggests that time preferences may vary over time, particularly
440 when farmers are exposed to distress of social nature (e.g., food shortages, health issues, vio-
441 lence or crime). These results align with (Bartos et al., 2018; Di Falco et al., 2019)Freudenreich
442 and Kebede (2022)Freudenreich & and Kebede (2022), who reported that Kenyan farmers expe-
443 riencing more shocks were increasingly likely to anticipate future shocks, hence adjusting their
444 behaviour accordingly.

445 Furthermore, we find no significant effects of setbacks of other type (economic, environmental),
446 which supports the idea that repeated exposure to distress can lead to desensitization under
447 specific conditions—namely, when the distress is of a social nature. This aligns with the findings
448 of Arias et al. (2019), who explored the association between conflict dynamics and households'
449 agricultural decisions, concluding that households may learn to adapt and operate amid social
450 distresses such as violence or conflicts. This contrasts with earlier studies that link impatience to
451 past negative economic experiences, such as agricultural input price increase or income reduc-
452 tion (Bartos et al., 2018; Di Falco et al., 2019).

453 (Tesfaye & Gebremariam, 2020)(Conte et al., 2023)Moreover, we find gender to be a prominent
454 factor associated with farmers' time preferences. This highlights the significant role that socio-
455 demographic characteristics play in shaping the heterogeneity of time preferences, despite the
456 lack of consensus in the existing literature. (Schechter & Francis, 2010). Finally, as expected, we
457 find a significant association between revealed risk and time preferences. Farmers with higher

458 propensity to take risks are also more prone to bet on a long-term remunerating investment. This
459 confirms the extant literature on risk attitudes and time preferences (e.g., Clot et al., 2016; Julia
460 Ihli et al., 2022) and the necessity of estimating both preferences jointly (Andersen et al., 2008).
461 Scholars have also highlighted that the relationship between risks and time preferences depends
462 on contextual elements (e.g., exogenous shocks, local history, demographic variables (Tanaka et
463 al., 2010), thus confirming the importance of investigating the role of past experiences in influenc-
464 ing individual's intertemporal and risk preferences.

465 These results are useful for policymakers in interpreting how African smallholder farmers might
466 make decisions over long-term spending and investments, purchasing habits, health and educa-
467 tion choices, in the aftermath of adverse social events. Our contribution is particularly relevant for
468 African fragile areas, where tensions and conflicts can result in quick deterioration of living con-
469 ditions and food security of farmers and communities living in rural contexts (Saulter, 2014). Given
470 the association between social distresses and farmers' time preferences, policy interventions and
471 research/sectorial strategies requiring farmers to modify their long-term spending and invest-
472 ments plans (e.g., for boosting agricultural productivity and innovation) should be carefully de-
473 signed and properly targeted. We believe that these interventions can be more effective when
474 implemented swiftly after a localised social distress (e.g., famines, conflicts). Our work has thus
475 direct implications for international agencies and national bodies aiming at transforming Africa's
476 agriculture to improve its competitiveness, speed up innovation adoptions, and globally fight food
477 insecurity.

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684 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relation-
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687 The data associated with this manuscript are archived in Zenodo ([https://doi.org/10.5281/ze-](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8413900)
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727 **Appendix A**

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Table A1. Average payoff across countries and experiments.

Country	Average payoff (number of tokens)		
	Risk prefer- ences	Time prefer- ences	Total
Kenya	107.1	125.3	232.4
Morocco	104.3	121.7	226
Tanzania	113.5	125.8	239.3
Tunisia	132.0	128.0	260
Uganda	99.9	134.2	234.1
Average	111.8	126.7	238.5

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731 **Appendix B**

732 **Table B1.** Estimated effects on farmers' patience (Tobit model coefficients with robust SE in pa-
 733 rentheses).

Variable	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
Social setbacks	1.622*** (0.515)	1.127** (0.508)	1.366*** (0.481)	1.305*** (0.496)
Economic setbacks	0.471 (0.823)	0.576 (0.813)	0.371 (0.798)	0.359 (0.796)
Environmental setbacks	0.927* (0.530)	-0.392 (0.521)	-0.652 (0.530)	-0.309 (0.543)
Social worries	-0.350 (0.600)	-0.080 (0.592)	-0.887 (0.558)	-0.951* (0.564)
Economic worries	-2.502*** (0.850)	-1.311 (0.823)	-2.087** (0.846)	-2.015** (0.846)
Environmental worries	0.916 (0.612)	0.776 (0.586)	0.898 (0.580)	0.842 (0.582)
Age (years)			-0.002 (0.014)	-0.009 (0.014)
Education: literate, no qualification			1.555 (1.081)	1.604 (1.104)
Education: literate with qualification			-0.146 (0.423)	-0.063 (0.428)
Gender (female = 1)			1.455*** (0.463)	1.347*** (0.511)
Income spent on food			-0.267 (0.392)	-0.068 (0.418)
Land/Pond size			11.076 (7.095)	10.771 (7.530)
Farmer's risk aversion (low)			0.636 (0.623)	0.447 (0.618)
Farmer's risk aversion (high)			0.114 (0.622)	0.016 (0.624)
Farmer's trust (low)			0.720 (0.659)	0.205 (0.665)

Farmer's trust (high)			1.208** (0.570)	1.154** (0.559)
Farmer's innovation (low)			0.488 (0.952)	0.546 (0.964)
Farmer's innovation (high)			-0.278 (0.749)	-0.458 (0.756)
Risk aversion level			-0.253*** (0.084)	-0.259*** (0.084)
Country FE	NO	YES	YES	YES
Session FE	NO	NO	NO	YES
Observations	1,938	1,938	1,181	1,181
McFadden's pseudo R ²	0.004	0.025	0.041	0.052
Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1				

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738 **Figure C1.** Frequency distribution of farmers' patience (switch point); aggregate data

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(N=1,938).

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741 **Figure C2.** Frequency distribution of farmers' patience (switch point) per country. KE= Kenya,

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MA = Morocco, TN = Tunisia, TZ = Tanzania, UG = Uganda.

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